

The Example of Perm Model in Substance Addiction, Especially with Alcohol and Gambling Examples

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Abstract

Numerous criteria are identified by independent researchers as essential factors for evaluating the efficacy of a program. The treatment approach is tailored to address the specific requirements of each patient, including any coexisting diseases such as chronic pain, anxiety, or hepatitis. The active encouragement of family engagement is a key aspect of the therapeutic process. Continuity of treatment is ensured throughout the advanced phases of rehabilitation via

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the establishment of active connections with several external resources. The property's meticulous attention to detail ensures the maintenance of a consistently pleasant disposition. Therapeutic services are grounded on empirical research and are formulated in accordance with contemporary industrial norms. The professionals within our organization have the necessary qualifications and have valid licenses and certifications in their respective areas of expertise. The program has received accreditation from a monitoring agency that is recognized at the national level. The monitoring of the patient's reaction to therapy is conducted, and the clinic or program furnishes outcome data that exhibits the efficacy of the treatment. In contemporary medical practice, drug use disorders are categorized by the particular substance that is being misused. As a consequence of this, a total of eleven distinct pathologies have been discovered. All of these phenomena possess inherent attributes that delineate addiction, including the capacity to promptly and passionately engage the brain's reward and reinforcement mechanisms. Frequently, this leads to the disregard of routine obligations and the promotion of excessive use accompanied by adverse outcomes. While the manifestation of withdrawal symptoms varies across different substances and may be absent in some drug categories like hallucinogens and inhalants, there are commonalities in the withdrawal symptoms experienced across numerous kinds of drugs. Alcohol, classified as a central nervous system depressant, is associated with the prevalence of alcohol use disorder. Notably, this condition exhibits a higher incidence among adult men, with a prevalence rate of 12.4%, compared to adult females, who exhibit a lower prevalence rate of 4.9%. It is worth noting, however, that rates of alcohol use disorder among females are seeing an upward trend.

Keywords: *Substance Addiction, Gambling Addiction, Alcohol Addiction, Perm Model, Struggling with Substance Addiction*

Introduction

Based on the findings of the study, it is evident that women have a heightened sensitivity towards some adverse consequences associated with alcohol intake. There are distinct impacts seen in both males and females, and these effects exhibit dissimilarities. The majority of individuals often exhibit signs of the illness many years prior to reaching the age of 40.

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Caffeine overdose, sometimes referred to as caffeine intoxication, manifests when excessive quantities of the stimulant are ingested, resulting in a diverse range of symptoms. This illness may manifest with symptoms such as restlessness, anxiety, sleeplessness, flushing, gastrointestinal issues, muscular twitching, disorganized thinking and speech, heart rhythm abnormalities, prolonged menstrual cycles, and psychomotor agitation. Excessive ingestion of caffeine may lead to the occurrence of caffeine poisoning in individuals. The incidence of cannabis use disorder has a negative correlation with age, with the largest occurrence seen among those aged 18 to 29, constituting the majority of affected individuals, at a rate of 4.8 percent. This phenomenon may be attributed to the fact that a significant proportion of individuals who engage in regular cannabis use fall within the young adult demographic.

Use of Phencyclidine and Other Hallucinogens May Cause Changes in Perception

The use of these chemicals has the potential to induce alterations in an individual's perception. Phencyclidine (PCP), sometimes referred to as "angel dust," is a hallucinogenic substance that induces a perceptual state characterized by a profound disconnect between cognitive processes and bodily experiences in those who use it. Volatile hydrocarbons are hazardous gases that are generated by inhalants, adhesives, fuels, paints, and other compounds with high volatility. Volatile substances are alternatively referred to as volatile compounds. The act of inhaling these gases, which possess the capacity to induce psychoactive effects, has the potential to result in sickness. The condition mostly affects individuals within the age range of 12 to 17, with a notable prevalence among those who are 12 years old. Opioid Use Disorder (OUD): Opioid drugs include a range of substances, including both illegal narcotics like heroin, as well as analgesics prescribed to patients such as oxycodone, codeine, morphine, and fentanyl. Heroin serves as an example of an illicit opioid substance. Prescription opioid medications include a range of substances, such as oxycodone, codeine, morphine, and fentanyl. Heroin is often recognized as the most infamous opioid drug. In a publication by the American Society of Addiction Medicine in 2015, it was reported that over 2 million individuals were grappling with drug addiction as a result of their

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utilization of prescription pain medication, while an additional 591,000 individuals were contending with substance abuse stemming from their use.

Methodology

In the United States, fatalities caused by opioid-related overdoses have exceeded those resulting from motor vehicle accidents, emerging as the primary cause of mortality among those under the age of fifty. According to the American Society for Addiction Medicine (ASAM), the administration of opioids to a patient serves as the primary catalyst for the development of addiction. This category encompasses the phenomenon of individuals developing addicted to sleep aids and anti-anxiety medicines, as well as the addictive nature of these drugs. Furthermore, within this cohort, there are issues pertaining to the use of sedatives and hypnotics. Alcohol and other chemical substances elicit a somewhat comparable neurological reaction. The prevalence of the illness is highest among those aged 18 to 29, since this age group exhibits the greatest susceptibility to disease exposure. Chemical substances that are included under the classification of stimulant use disorder comprise cocaine, amphetamines, and methylphenidate, which is more often recognized by its brand name Ritalin. Ritalin is only available as a medication that requires a prescription. Stimulant medicine is often used as the primary therapeutic intervention for attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) and narcolepsy. Cocaine use is mostly prevalent within the demographic of young people ranging from 18 to 25 years of age inside the United States. Nicotine, a central nervous system stimulant, plays a pivotal role in the formation of tobacco addiction.

Use Disorder

Research findings indicate that a considerable proportion, namely 68 percent, of adult individuals who engage in smoking express a desire to cease this habit. Moreover, it has been observed that around 50 percent of smokers have undertaken at least one endeavor to quit smoking at some juncture in their lifetimes. A diverse range of pharmaceutical substances, including antihistamines,

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palm nut, cortisol, and steroids, may exert influences on the central nervous system, potentially resulting in obsessive use and consequential adverse outcomes.

The phenomenon of gambling and several other manifestations of compulsive behavior or addiction the image used in this work is credited to Joshua Resnick and is sourced from Shutterstock. The scope of addiction extends beyond the use of chemicals like cocaine, alcohol, inhalants, and biological agents like nicotine. Various forms of obsessive habits or addictions also come under this particular group. One may consider including activities that provide the possibility for immediate pleasure as a prospective incentive. Activities that provide prompt feedback possess the characteristic of swiftly transitioning from innocuous enjoyment to an obsessive pursuit of rewards. The reason for this phenomenon might be attributed to the prompt and timely feedback that is inherent in these activities. This phenomenon may result in individuals deviating from their pursuit of other essential life objectives, so giving rise to a multitude of adverse outcomes, including financial loss and the deterioration of vital interpersonal connections.

One potential behavioral manifestation suggestive of a gambling problem is the inclination to engage in gambling activities with progressively larger monetary sums in order to get the desired degree of stimulation sought by the person.

1. *The individual has sensations of unease or discomfort while endeavoring to diminish their engagement in gaming activities or cease gambling entirely.*
2. *The significance lies in the historical record of futile efforts aimed at diminishing or eradicating gaming activities. The primary focus of your thoughts is on gambling activities and casino games.*
3. *Experiencing emotional distress and engaging in gambling activities as a consequence of that distress.*
4. *The individual who has incurred financial setbacks as a result of gambling afterwards tries to compensate for these losses.*
5. *The practice of deceitfully concealing the amount of money used on gambling activities.*
6. *The concept of responsible gambling entails refraining from compromising significant relationships, employment, education, or other obligations as a result of one's engagement in gaming activities.*

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7. 7. *An individual's unfavorable economic circumstances necessitating the pursuit of financial aid from other sources.*

The most current version of the International Classification of Diseases was revised by the World Health Organization (WHO) in June 2018, including the addition of a new illness. Gaming Disorder is distinguished by an excessive engagement in online games or video games, whereby the individual consistently prioritizes these activities above other interests and pursuits, despite the potential adverse consequences associated with such activity. This phenomenon may occur regardless of whether the game is being played on a personal computer or a dedicated video game console. The involvement in this endeavor serves as a manifestation of the agreement attained by professionals hailing from diverse fields of study and geographical regions around the globe. The authors emphasize the observation that only a minority of individuals who participate in activities such as video gaming or internet browsing are susceptible to being diagnosed. Specifically, those who possess little agency over the aforementioned activity and allocate an inordinate amount of time engaging in this activity are susceptible to potential negative outcomes. Presently, scholars in the United States are engaged in an exploration of the potential correlation between certain patterns of excessive conduct, including mobile phone use, online gambling and gaming, pornography consumption, as well as indulgence in eating and shopping, and the underlying etiology of behavioral problems. While participating in such activities provides several opportunities for immediate gratification, it remains uncertain whether they fulfill all the requirements necessary to be classified as addictive behavior.

Literature Review

Based on the findings of the Drug Abuse and Mental Health Services Administration (2019), it has been approximated that the number of individuals in the United States who satisfy the established criteria for a drug use disorder exceeds 20 million. Substance use disorders have a significant impact on a diverse range of individuals, including veterans, medical professionals, athletes, young

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individuals, and those with concurrent mental and physical health issues (Cuffel, 1996; Aarons et al., 2001; Oreskovich et al., 20). Certain individuals have a higher propensity for developing a drug use problem compared to others. According to Hesselbrock et al. (1999), de Wit and Phan (2010), and Berridge and Robinson (2016), The researchers have discovered data that substantiates many ideas related to the neurological, emotional, and behavioral aspects of drug use, hence confirming the validity of these perspectives.

Important Data

Nevertheless, the integration of crucial tenets from positive psychology into current studies on substance abuse has not been accomplished by scholars. The PERMA model, which posits that positive emotions, engagement, relationships, meaning, and accomplishments contribute to disparities in happiness (Seligman, 2011), might potentially provide valuable insights into the motivations behind drug usage among people. This conclusion may be attributed to the PERMA paradigm, which posits that variations in happiness can be elucidated by pleasant emotions, commitment, meaningful relationships, and significant accomplishments. This is due to the fact that the PERMA framework facilitates the attainment of genuine happiness in people. This elucidates the formidable challenges faced by individuals grappling with substance abuse issues in their endeavors to abstain from or diminish their use of drugs.

The PERMA model encompasses a variety of behaviors, including both those unrelated to drug use and those that exemplify behaviors associated with substance misuse. Positive emotions refer to a range of subjective experiences that are characterized by pleasant feelings, such as joy, happiness, and contentment. The positive emotions component pertains to the phenomenon of engaging in activities and encountering events that lead to feelings of pleasure or behavioral rewards in the context of drug use (Seligman, 2011). Engaging in drug-related activities and circumstances might elicit positive emotional experiences. Engaging in activities and encounters that elicit pleasure may lead individuals to subsequently feel pleasant emotions. There has been a longstanding assumption in the literature that drug use behaviors, which refer to actions that lead to immediate pleasure or satisfaction from drug use (Berridge & Robinson, 2016), are primarily

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motivated by behavioral reward systems. Furthermore, contemporary research endeavors have included principles derived from the field of behavioral economics in their investigations pertaining to substance abuse issues. The findings of this study indicate that drug use behaviors are strengthened by the presence and perceived immediate utility of incentives associated with substance use, despite the potential long-term repercussions of these rewards (Murphy et al., 2012; Bickel et al., 2014; Teeters and Murphy, 2015).

Consequently, medicines elicit quick behavioral reinforcements by inducing enjoyable experiences, often leading to the perception of good affect. The PERMA paradigm posits that individuals may enhance their overall well-being by cultivating a consistent practice of engaging in activities that elicit good feelings. Individuals may engage in substance use as a means to enhance their affective state and subsequently augment their participation in non-drug related activities, such as exercise. The term "drug-free" is used to describe activities that do not entail the use or use of drugs. Within the context of therapeutic interventions, it is possible to mitigate the addictive tendencies arising from narcotics by using redirection techniques and promoting behavioral activation towards alternative activities that elicit pleasure sensations, therefore compensating for the positive feelings associated with drug usage that patients have grown dependent on. In essence, therapeutic interventions have the potential to supplant the pleasurable affective encounters that individuals develop a dependency on as a consequence of substance abuse, by fostering engagement in pursuits that elicit sensations of happiness.

In essence, therapeutic interventions may serve as a means of mitigating the addictive tendencies that individuals develop towards drugs by addressing and substituting for the pleasant emotional experiences associated with such dependencies. Modifying the conditions that give rise to positive emotions is a challenge, but one that is not insurmountable. Emergency management is a crucial component of therapy, as shown in a thorough study conducted by Prendergast et al. (2006). The treatment has shown the ability to induce feelings of optimism.

Therefore, it is essential for therapists to redirect their clients' attention towards the perception of enjoyable feelings, most of which arise from pursuits unrelated to substance abuse. In the event that this circumstance does not transpire, it is conceivable for people to develop a dependence on drugs as a means to attain enjoyable emotional states. As per the PERMA model proposed by

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Seligman (2011), commitment may be described as a cognitive state that arises when a person is totally engaged and interested in an activity that brings them pleasure. Individuals who face challenges in experiencing commitment, such as constrained living conditions resulting from excessive work hours to sustain their livelihood, mental health issues like depressed anhedonia, or disabilities that impede their ability to leave their homes due to safety concerns, are at an increased risk for substance use. This association has been documented in previous studies (Cuffel, 1996; Moore and Li, 1998; Silverman et al., 2019).

Engaging in Substance Use

Several studies have shown that substances such as nicotine, cannabis, LSD (also known as acid), amphetamines, and MDMA (often referred to as ecstasy or molly) have the potential to augment one's subjective experience (Gilbert and Gilbert, 1998; Zeiger et al, 2010; Holze et al, 2020). Numerous individuals assert the capacity to notably augment their subjective sense of pleasure in various domains, such as gastronomy, sexual encounters, auditory stimulation, and engagement in nature-induced mystical encounters. Consequently, people may often resort to substance abuse as an expedient means to enhance their engagement in activities or even routine duties when their innate capacity for involvement in enjoyable activities is insufficient or inaccessible. In line with the phenomenon of deriving positive emotions from non-substance incentives, mental health practitioners may contemplate the implementation of therapeutic strategies aimed at enhancing clients' involvement in substance-free activities. This can be achieved through two primary avenues: firstly, engaging in collaborative problem-solving with clients to optimize the duration and availability of enjoyable experiences, akin to the principles of behavioral activation (i.e., the deliberate planning and assessment of emotional states during pleasurable activities; Dimidjian et al., 2021).

The subsequent stage involves imparting pupils with practical skills that have a direct impact on enhancing their overall learning experience. The aforementioned talents include the concept of taste as derived from the realm of positive psychology, as well as the notion of awareness of the present moment as derived from the domain of acceptance and commitment therapy (Bryan et al.,

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2022; Stone and Schmidt, 2022). Clinicians use both of these proficiencies to enhance non-substance-related enjoyable experiences, hence mitigating the need for medication in promoting engagement in activities.

Links

In accordance with the PERMA model proposed by Seligman (2011), establishing meaningful interpersonal relationships is an additional factor that enhances the experience of genuine joy in one's life. While it is well acknowledged that drug misuse may strain an individual's social connections (Daley, 2013), it is worth noting that there exist two potential mechanisms via which substance abuse may paradoxically contribute to the strengthening of social relationships. Initially, individuals may choose for pharmacological interventions to enhance their interpersonal interactions, such as mitigating irritation or bolstering self-esteem. There are other approaches available to accomplish this task. For instance, alcohol is often used in social contexts as a means for individuals to establish connections with others (Collins et al., 1985; Monahan and Lannutti, 2000). This phenomenon may be attributed to the ability of alcohol to induce a sense of ease and relaxation in individuals while in social settings. Individuals that engage in drug use have a significant benefit in terms of their connection to the culture around substance use (Moshier et al., 2012; Calvo et al., 2016). Individuals who engaged in substance usage reported experiencing heightened feelings of social connectedness and a greater sense of belonging within their own communities. Dinges and Oetting (1993) and Donohew et al. (1999) have shown that a considerable proportion of individuals establish social bonds with other drug users, afterwards using substance usage as a means to foster connection within this particular social circle. Hence, the use of substances engenders a perception of communal integration and affiliation, while concurrently facilitating interpersonal communication within social settings. This phenomenon may be attributed to the facilitation of social bonding among persons by drugs.

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Findings

Based on the research performed by Knight and Simpson (1996) as well as Falkin and Strauss (2003), it has been shown that persons who engage in drug consumption are more prone to relapse and engaging in more hazardous drug use when they associate with peers or family members who also partake in drug use. That is the reason why partnerships are presently the focal point of several therapeutic approaches. It is important for physicians to provide patients the chance to cultivate a feeling of community and belonging that transcends subcultures and individuals who engage in substance abuse. The use of this approach may lead to a reduction in patients' reliance on their affiliation with a group of persons who either currently use or have successfully abstained from the substances they are attempting to stop. While drugs may enhance social interaction, it is important to note that they do not provide a definitive solution to underlying issues, such as poor self-esteem or social anxiety. Patients may have improved communication abilities when they possess the necessary information and have access to therapeutic interventions that enable them to manage distressing emotions without relying on pharmacological interventions. Consequently, individuals will have a reduced inclination to resort to drugs throughout their social interactions. The term "meaning" as used in the PERMA framework refers to the perception that an individual's existence has a purpose and the consistency of occurrences encountered throughout the course of one's life.

Argument

Seligman (2011) posits that the concept of meaning may be characterized as the subjective perception that one's life has a sense of purpose, together with the perceived coherence and continuity of the many experiences encountered over one's lifespan. According to Stone and Parks (2018), humans possess the capacity to derive meaning from many circumstances, including familial membership, occupational pursuits, and the use of personal skills and interests. In the pursuit of comprehending the significance of substance usage, several individuals have conveyed instances of encountering mystical, spiritual, or religious phenomena as a consequence of their engagements with psychoactive substances (2017). These people articulate their subjective

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accounts pertaining to the consequences stemming from their engagements with psychoactive substances. Furthermore, the acquisition of substances, such as narcotics, which may need a certain degree of proficiency for their appropriate use (e.g., accurate administration of heroin through injection or proper inhalation of methamphetamine), as well as participating in actions while under the influence, might provide favorable outcomes.

Person with a Sense of Purpose in His Life

As to the American Psychiatric Association (2013), a significant number of individuals grappling with substance use issues acknowledge the elevated significance attributed to drug or alcohol use in their life. The inadequacy of this meaning and purpose, as shown by the findings of Csabonyi and Phillips (2020), lies in its inability to effectively fulfill their expectations. As a consequence of devoting a significant amount of time to drug use and acquisition, individuals experience a decline in their capacity to pursue and engage in activities and endeavors that might provide their lives with a deeper and enduring feeling of significance and purpose. Although these behaviors do provide a certain degree of purpose and meaning, they also impose constraints on an individual's ability to achieve such fulfillment. The fundamental principle behind the 12 step programs is the cultivation of a spiritual relationship with a higher power, which serves as a means to explore and ascertain one's existential significance and objectives, as well as to liberate oneself from the grip of addiction. Individuals who engage in 12-step programs publicly pledge their allegiance to a supreme being and are expected to maintain transparency with such entity on their shortcomings in achieving certain criteria. Certain individuals have achieved success in 12-step programs; nevertheless, these programs include many limitations. These drawbacks encompass a negative framework (Stone, in press), a religious aspect that may not be applicable to all individuals, and unexpected consequences in terms of success (Flanagin, 2014). Notwithstanding these limitations, there are individuals who achieve success in 12-step programs. Consequently, more investigation is required on therapeutic interventions that foster the cultivation and enhancement of patients' sense of meaning and purpose, in conjunction with the use of the 12-step program.

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Numerous positive psychological therapies, such as Life Story or goal setting (Stone & Parks, 2018), have promising potential for efficacy. Nevertheless, a full investigation into the use of these interventions specifically for drug use disorders has yet to be undertaken by researchers (Stone, in press). Nevertheless, if medical professionals are able to assist their patients in discovering significance and direction in their life outside the realm of drug use, it is plausible that these people would exhibit reduced inclination to engage in substance abuse. The objective may be achieved via assisting patients in the exploration and identification of the significance and direction of their life outside the realm of substance abuse. The accomplishments or successes that an individual or group has attained. Seligman (2011) posits that the last and pivotal element of the PERMA model pertains to an individual's ability to attain significant and purposeful accomplishments. Amphetamines have been reported to be used by individuals as a means to enhance academic performance in college (Varga, 2012). Furthermore, alcohol consumption has been observed to be employed by individuals as a strategy to facilitate social interactions and establish friendships (Collins et al., 1985; Monahan and Lannutti, 2000). Additionally, LSD has been suggested to be utilized by individuals as a means to foster creative thinking (Janiger and De Rios, 1989).

Individuals may use chemicals as a means to attain a diverse range of objectives. DeSantis and Hane (2010) propose that some individuals may use these objectives as a rationale for perpetuating or initiating drug consumption. According to the findings of Bayard et al. (2004), the treatment of an individual's drug use issues may provide greater challenges when the drugs in question provide some functional benefits to the person. This scenario might arise if an individual engages in self-medication (Laroche et al., 2012), seeks assistance within their professional or educational environment (DeSantis & Hane, 2010), or use drug usage as a means to facilitate religious encounters (Pahnke, 1967). The phrase "self-medication" is used by Laroche et al. (2012). DeSantis and House (2010) conducted a study.

Consequently, the primary objective of drug addiction therapy is to mitigate or eradicate the use of addictive substances, while concurrently assisting patients in enhancing their functionality and attaining their objectives. This intervention will serve as a supplementary measure in aiding patients to decrease or cease their drug use. Understanding the underlying factors contributing to

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individuals' challenges in attaining optimal functioning and goal attainment should be a primary area of emphasis in endeavors aimed at facilitating their achievement of objectives and promoting normal functioning, without reliance on psychoactive drugs. The therapies used should be tailored to address the specific issue presented by the patient. For instance, if an individual resorts to alcohol consumption as a means of overcoming social anxiety and making friends, including exposure therapy into the treatment regimen for drug use may effectively diminish the incentive to persist in such behavior.

Using Alcohol

Moreover, a considerable segment of the population may exhibit ambivalence towards the use of pharmaceutical substances to attain their objectives. In such instances, the application of motivational interviewing, as proposed by Lundahl and Burke (2009), might serve as a valuable strategy to address and resolve this state of indecisiveness. Hence, by addressing the root causes of drug use and assisting clients in attaining their objectives without resorting to substance use, therapists may potentially mitigate clients' inclination to engage in drug use, contingent upon the motivations behind their substance use. It is crucial for therapists to effectively address the fundamental factors contributing to drug use and assist clients in attaining their objectives of abstinence. The following discourse elucidates the rationales for the assertion that drug usage fails to engender genuine happiness in one's life. Considering the potential for substance use to interact with each of the five components of the PERMA model, it is understandable that individuals may question why engagement in drug use fails to result in a really fulfilling and contented existence. The answer may be divided into two main aspects. Firstly, people resort to substance use as a temporary means of addressing the challenges they encounter in life. Secondly, the continued use of drugs is not a viable long-term solution, leading individuals to engage in repetitive substance use. While drug use may elicit emotions of happiness, facilitate engagement in pleasurable pursuits, and foster social bonding, a significant portion of these experiences are forfeited upon cessation of substance use. This stands in opposition to the cultivation of aptitudes and pursuits that are disconnected from drug use, possess enduring qualities, and do not include the use of substances. Furthermore, it is important to acknowledge that while substances may yield positive

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outcomes, they are also linked to various adverse repercussions. These include financial challenges and homelessness, strained interpersonal connections, concerns regarding physical well-being, legal complications, and unemployment (Eyrich, Garg et al., 2008; Brook et al., 2009; Daley, 2013; Compton et al., 2014; Moore et al., 2020). Numerous researches have documented these adverse outcomes. Therefore, the misuse of substances might provide immediate gratification in one's existence, but it is not a sustainable remedy and often entails a diverse range of unfavorable repercussions. Considering the novelty of this article's application of the PERMA model to the issue of drug misuse, several potential avenues for further exploration emerge. One potential approach to empirically examine the suitability of the PERMA model for this particular demographic is through the implementation of rigorous research or studies. These investigations would aim to thoroughly evaluate the extent to which the case conceptualization of individuals who use drugs or have substance use issues aligns with the situational conceptualization, thereby assessing the applicability and congruence of the PERMA model.

PERMA Model

This will serve as a demonstration of the applicability of the PERMA model to the aforementioned population. Researchers have the opportunity to create and evaluate a multidimensional scale using the PERMA paradigm in order to directly assess drug usage. The effectiveness and potential benefits of a treatment program specifically intended to address the components of the PERMA model for drug use disorders remain uncertain. The insufficiency of evidence to substantiate any of these ideas is the underlying reason for this assertion. The existing literature study did not thoroughly investigate the potential effectiveness of the PERMA model in addressing drug use disorders to the extent that would have been possible if it had been performed using digital resources instead of relying on traditional paper-based format. This restriction was imposed by the constraints inherent to the paper format.

Hence, doing further study in this domain might be advantageous. Conducting comprehensive study on this subject has the potential to unveil more knowledge that may serve as a foundation for further investigations and scholarly inquiries. Academics, as a collective, are faced with a

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substantial workload that remains to be addressed. However, there exist several prospects for innovative and progressive approaches to tackle these challenges.

The objective of this study is to formulate hypotheses, provide empirical research, and explore the potential applications of the PERMA model in the context of drug treatment. Specifically, this study aims to investigate the underlying factors that drive people to engage in drug use. Furthermore, the objective of this project is to do research on the use of this model within the context of treatment. Upon careful examination, it becomes apparent that despite the constraints imposed by the limited availability of data and the relatively recent emergence of this field of study, the research findings provide substantial support for the use of the PERMA model as a conceptual framework in the context of drug use. This phenomenon remains true, although supported by recent research. The utilization of drugs by individuals to enhance or expedite gratification across several aspects of life has the capacity to result in maladaptive substance usage and the development of substance use disorders. The complex nature of the quest of pleasure is evident in all five of these domains. This phenomenon persists, despite the possibility of achieving a content and harmonious existence by actively pursuing fulfillment in all five domains. The present study aims to advocate for the adoption of a specific framework by therapists in their conceptualization of clients diagnosed with substance use disorders. Furthermore, it emphasizes the need of directing therapeutic interventions towards the use of non-pharmacological alternatives, with the ultimate goal of facilitating the development of a fulfilling and addiction-free life for patients.

Addictions to Substances

Furthermore, it is important to promote the use of this framework among therapists in their conceptualization of individuals presenting with mental health illnesses. The care and advocacy approach to mental health and addiction care, also known as "behavioral health," has been providing financial support to treatment facilities for the last five decades, while awaiting the arrival of individuals with behavioral health issues. The outcome entails an unceasing need that is unattainable. According to the National Survey on Drug Use and Health, the utilization of mental

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health services among adults with any mental illness was estimated to be 45% in 2019. Similarly, only 10% of individuals aged twelve and above with a substance use disorder received treatment for their condition. These estimates align with the data from the preceding four years. Current advancements in behavioral health policy include the pursuit of equitable allocation of financing and the broadening of accessibility to behavioral health treatment, within the context of broader health reform initiatives.

The potential consequences of this concussion may manifest as any of the aforementioned medical conditions. If left unaddressed, emotional stress has the potential to escalate and manifest in an exacerbated manner, necessitating the adoption of unhealthy coping mechanisms such as drug abuse or engaging in obsessive activities like excessive shopping, gambling, or sexual activity in order to alleviate the internal turmoil.

Addiction and Trauma

Females have a heightened fear reaction, rendering them twice as prone as males to the onset of post-traumatic stress disorder subsequent to experiencing a traumatic incident. Female individuals who are exposed to or see instances of domestic violence have a tendency to engage in violent behavior themselves, in addition to engaging in drug abuse. There are other high-risk and unmanageable methods, such as engaging in promiscuous sexual activity (which may contribute to the emergence of compulsive sexual behavior) or engaging in self-harm, including slashing the skin. Although not indicative of suicidal intent, the experience of acute pain serves as a temporary respite from the emotional strain associated with domestic violence. Children may have significant impairment as a result of the emotional strain they endure when exposed to domestic abuse. When parents exhibit anger and engage in conflict in the presence of their children, it is often seen that youngsters struggle to comprehend the nature of the situation. The potential ramifications of this phenomenon on the cognitive development of children are often seen in the manifestation of heightened levels of worry or stress. Indeed, it is evident that the disparities endure into adulthood, hence resulting in notable distinctions between the neural

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structures of those raised in secure and nurturing family environments compared to those raised in households characterized by domestic violence.

Childhood Trauma and Lifetime Addiction

According to a publication in the Journal of Neuropsychopharmacology, the observed distinction may be attributed to impairments in neural connectivity among regions responsible for the integration of emotion and cognition. Additionally, the insula, a central brain structure, is also implicated in this phenomenon. Adolescents who experienced childhood domestic violence often have cognitive challenges in regulating their emotions and subsequent behavioral responses. Children have a tendency to absorb the challenges they face, with some even assuming guilt and assuming responsibility for the abusive actions of their parents. In the absence of appropriate treatment for trauma, children's cognitive processes may be hindered in assimilating the sensory stimuli associated with abusive experiences. Consequently, they may resort to engaging in compulsive behaviors or substance misuse as a means of seeking consolation. The number provided by the user is 19. Failure to provide treatment for trauma in children might result in detrimental effects on their brain development. Adolescents transition into adulthood with a propensity for harboring profound animosity and resentment towards their parents, along with a deficiency in self-assurance. Nevertheless, they often lack the necessary knowledge and aptitude to effectively address these challenges. However, many instead turn to engaging in harmful behaviors and drug abuse as a means of finding comfort. According to The Fix, the amalgamation of these several causes leads to the establishment of a lifetime addiction as a consequence of childhood trauma. In a study published in the academic journal Depression and Anxiety, a group of researchers conducted a survey including a sample size of 587 individuals. The study revealed a significant and robust statistical association between childhood abuse, encompassing sexual, emotional, or physical forms, and the manifestation of drug use as a symptom of post-traumatic stress disorder.

The proportion of participants who engaged in drug misuse due to the post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) they encountered. The experience of childhood maltreatment has the capacity to

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inflict lasting harm upon the psychological well-being of the kid, hence increasing the probability of further victimization. Traumatic brain injuries are prevalent among athletes participating in contact sports, including football, boxing, wrestling, and ice hockey. Traumatic brain injuries (TBIs) manifest as a result of a forceful impact to the head, causing the brain to collide with the inner walls of the skull, hence leading to the disruption and tearing of nerve fibers. One of the several consequences associated with such injuries is the impairment of neural circuits responsible for transmitting signals related to pleasure and amusement. The disruption of reward pathways in individuals who use drugs has resemblance to the disruption seen in cases of traumatic brain injuries. Consequently, athletes with such injuries have an elevated risk of developing substance use-related issues, perhaps attributable to the stimulatory impact. The integrity of the motivational brain circuitry has been compromised.

The author reported on research which revealed that a range of 20 percent to 30 percent of individuals who had a traumatic brain injury (TBI) subsequently developed an addiction. Furthermore, head traumas might manifest as several different forms of harm. The significant magnitude of strain experienced by sportsmen sometimes leads to the misuse of painkillers and steroids as a means to alleviate discomfort.

Conclusion

Consequently, these sportsmen often manifest drug addiction tendencies as they persist in engaging in substance misuse. On an entirely another magnitude, individuals who have served in the military and are reintegrating into civilian life after their deployment have elevated levels of drug abuse. In addition to enduring persistent and chronic pain and tiredness, soldiers have an equal susceptibility to experiencing traumatic brain damage as a consequence of their occupational duties. Moreover, the presence of war environments and the encounters troops face contribute to an increased susceptibility to post-traumatic stress disorder. The confluence of these elements is very likely to culminate in the development of addiction. The predicament faced by law enforcement officials is equally challenging. The prevalence of post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) among those working in correctional facilities is much higher compared to veterans who

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have served in the military, mostly due to the demanding, distressing, and sometimes degrading nature of their professions. Certain indicators of PTSD (excessive alertness, flashbacks, suicidal thoughts, and depression) were discovered in 34 percent of prison officers, compared with only 14 percent among veterans, according to the findings of a clinical investigator specializing in dealing with law enforcement. The Relationship Between Emotional Stress and Addiction According to Maia Szalavitz's 2016 publication titled "The Unbroken Brain: A Revolutionary New Way to Understand Addiction," individuals grappling with addiction experience a loss of control over their compulsions, including the decision to take drugs, due to the overwhelming influence of emotional stress. Activities such as gambling, excessive eating, and shopping, among others. Former law enforcement personnel acknowledge that their primary method of managing the psychological strain encountered in their professional roles is via the use of substances such as narcotics and alcohol for self-medication purposes. According to the Washington Post, those who engage in addictive activities exhibit a lack of resistance to the allure of their psyche due to the constant strain and stress experienced by their cognitive faculties. When considering the matter from this perspective, it becomes apparent that moral model theories attributing addiction to greed and hedonism lack validity. Instead, it is evident that individuals struggling with addiction often encounter feelings of anxiety, sadness, or trauma, which may stem from or be a consequence of a suppressed or deeply ingrained incident or experience.

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